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Consecutive Days Without Rain in Italian Regions

They decreased by 2.12% between 2011 and 2022

Istat calculates the consecutive days without rain. Days without rain are defined as the maximum number of consecutive days in the year with daily precipitation less than or equal to 1 mm. The data refers to the Italian regions in the period between 2011 and 2022.

Ranking of the regions by value of consecutive days without rain in the Italian regions in 2022. Sardinia is in first place by value of consecutive days without rain in 2022 with a value of 74, followed by Sicily with a value of 46 and Veneto with a value of 36. In the middle of the table is Lazio with a value of 27 units, followed by Liguria and Trentino Alto Adige with a value of 25 units. Molise, Campania and Basilicata close the ranking with a value of 21.

Ranking of the regions by value of the percentage change in consecutive days without rain between 2011 and 2022. Sardinia is in first place for percentage change in consecutive days without rain between 2011 and 2022 with a corresponding value of 94.74%. to a variation from an amount of 38 units up to a value of 74 units. Piedmont follows with a variation equal to 50% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 22 units up to a value of 33 units. In third place is Veneto with a percentage variation of 50.00% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 24 units up to a value of 36 units. In the middle of the table are the Marche with a variation equal to +22.22% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 18 units up to a value of 22 units. Liguria follows with a variation equal to +19.05% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 21 units up to a value of 25 units. Emilia Romagna follows with a variation equal to an amount of 13.64% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 22 units up to a value of 25 units. Calabria closes the ranking with a variation equal to -42.11% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 38 units up to a value of 22 units, followed by Sicily with a variation equal to -48.60% corresponding to a variation from 89.5 units and from Puglia with a variation from an amount of 45 units up to a value of 22 units. On average, consecutive days without rain in Italian regions decreased by 2.12% between 2011 and 2022.

Consecutive days without rain in the Italian macro-regions between 2011 and 2022. The trend of consecutive days without rain was fluctuating in the Italian macro-regions between 2011 and 2022. In fact, there are macro-regions in which the days consecutive periods without rain decreased and others in which they increased. The macro-regions characterized by an increase in the value of consecutive days without rain are the North with a value of +12.50%, the North West with +31.82%, the North-East with +8.33%, the Central Italy with +12.50% and the Islands with +20.00%. The macro-regions in which consecutive days without rain have decreased are the South with a value of -28.95%, the South with -34.38%. Therefore, the regions of the Centre-North were characterized by an increase in the value of consecutive days without rain while, on the contrary, the southern regions were characterized by a reduction of the same value.

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Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. For this purpose, three clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Liguria, Abruzzo, Valle d'Aosta, Trentino Alto Adige, Lombardy, Marche, Piedmont, Emilia-Romagna, Molise, Tuscany, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Veneto, Umbria;
- Cluster 2: Campania, Puglia, Calabria, Basilicata, Lazio;
- Cluster 3: Sicily, Sardinia.

If we consider the average of the clusters, we can notice the following ordering: $C3 > C2 > C1$. That is, the reduction in rainy days mainly affected two regions, namely Sicily and Sardinia. In second place are other central-southern regions, in which the reduction in rainy days was consistent, i.e. those represented in C2. Finally, there are the regions of cluster 3, which are essentially central-northern regions with the exception of Molise and Abruzzo. It follows that the reduction in rainy days is essentially a phenomenon of the southern regions and Lazio.

Conclusions. Consecutive days without rain decreased by 2.12% between 2011 and 2022 in Italian regions. In general, the value of consecutive days without rain increased in the central-northern macro-regions and decreased in the southern macro-regions. However, some southern regions, such as Sicily and Sardinia, have very high levels of days without rain. Therefore, the data show a reduction in rainfall in the central-northern regions and an increase in the southern regions with the exception of the Islands. Obviously, the reduction in rainy days can lead to negative effects on agriculture and the distribution of water resources, especially in the northern regions, which are also characterized by the presence of very advanced agricultural companies from a technical-organisational point of view.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

Rank	Regione	2011	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
1	Sardegnia	38	74	36	94,74
2	Piemonte	22	33	11	50
3	Veneto	24	36	12	50
4	Lombardia	23	32	9	39,13

5	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	24	30	6	25
6	Abruzzo	17	21	4	23,53
7	Molise	17	21	4	23,53
8	Toscana	22	27	5	22,73
9	Marche	18	22	4	22,22
10	Liguria	21	25	4	19,05
11	Emilia-Romagna	22	25	3	13,64
12	Umbria	24	27	3	12,5
13	Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	24	25	1	4,17
14	Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	23	21	-2	-8,7
15	Lazio	33	27	-6	-18,18
16	Basilicata	31	21	-10	-32,26
17	Campania	35	21	-14	-40
18	Calabria	38	22	-16	-42,11
19	Sicilia	89,5	46	-43,5	-48,6
20	Puglia	45	22	-23	-51,11

	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Piemonte	22	21	18	17	21	21	29	13	28	26	16	33
Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	23	14	18	17	16	20	15	11	17	21	16	21
Liguria	21	22	16	16	19	23	19	13,5	27	23	17	25
Lombardia	23	22	18	17	22	39	21	15	27	26	21	32
Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	24	13	18	19	21	37	21	12	19,5	24	21	25
Veneto	24	22	24	18	22	39	42	12	24	27	21	36
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	24	14	23	19	21	37	44	11	20	27	18	30
Emilia-Romagna	22	25	24	17	22	39	18	14	28	27	20	25
Toscana	22	33	23	17	21	24	21	13	27	27	22	27
Umbria	24	24	22	16	27	35	30	14	27	27	23	27
Marche	18	21	23	12	21	35	20	13	24	22	25	22
Lazio	33	24	22	17	22	35	36	14	27	27	31	27
Abruzzo	17	19	21	15	15	23	16	11	17	19	21	21
Molise	17	27	23	15	21	22	15	11	22	22	28	21
Campania	35	47	22	21	24	35	36	15	29	27	35	21
Puglia	45	48	23	24	25	35	32	19	37	26	30	22
Basilicata	31	37	22	24	24	35	30	17	26	27	29	21
Calabria	38	47	22	24	23	19	32	16	28	30	34	22
Sicilia	89,5	56	37	46	31	31,5	53	36	44	40	38	46
Sardegna	38	56	32	32	34	37	65	26	49	44	47	74

	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Nord	24	22	18	17	22	35	22	13	27	26	20	27

Nord-ovest	22	22	18	17	21	23	21	13	27	26	18	29
Nord-est	24	22	23	18	22	37	22	12	26	27	21	26
Centro	24	25	23	17	21	35	23	13	27	27	25	27
Mezzogiorno	38	48	23	25	25	34	37	19	37	29	35	27
Sud	32	39	22	23	24	23	29	15	25	26	31	21
Isole	47,5	56	36	37	34	37	59	36	47	43,5	43,5	57